

Educational Problems of Muslim Girl's Students at Secondary and Higher Secondary School Education of Paschim Medinipur District in West Bengal

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Abstract: “Education is not only the right, but the duty of every Muslim, male or female. The best gift from a father to his child is education and upbringing. Knowledge cannot be acquired with sloth.” Education is the key factor for any kind of human development, prosperity and welfare of any society. As we are all aware, education is necessary for optimal growth. It is especially true for women, who make up a weaker and more marginalized segment of society. We have a significant gap in our knowledge and comprehension of Muslim culture from an experienced point of view since there are so few social science research studies on Muslims in India, specifically Muslim women from West Bengal. Because they were not exposed to contemporary schooling, Muslim women sometimes engage in cultural and social events more than do women of other religions. The current study makes an effort to analyse the educational challenges faced by Muslim girls enrolled in Paschim Medinipur's secondary and upper secondary schools in West Bengal. The descriptive survey approach was used as the investigational strategy for the current research. The sample for the current research included 150 Muslim females from 10 upper secondary schools in the Paschim Medinipur District, 60 of who were dropouts, including 75 rural, 75 urban, and 30 rural and 30 urban Muslim girls. The researcher created her own questionnaire to learn about the issues facing the sampled females. The survey found no discernible difference between Muslim females from rural and urban areas in terms of issues with securing scholarships and dropping out of higher education. However, the investigator discovered a considerable disparity in the occurrence of discrimination and harassment of Muslim females in upper secondary school in rural and urban areas.

Keywords: Problems, Rural and Urban Muslim Girls, Higher Secondary School Education.

INTRODUCTION:

Human beings are the excellent creation of Almighty God. Because as if compared to other Biological creature he is not cantered only on ‘Food’, ‘Fear’, ‘Sleep’, and ‘Sex’. Beyond that he created the well cultured society. Today he is even able to create a pro-universe with help of mind power, intelligence provided by the God. “Man becomes Man through Education”. In terms of pursuing modern education, Muslims and other populations in the nation are now almost proportionately equal, although Muslims still lag behind in terms of acquiring professional and technical education. Competition is required for admittance to these programmes, and Muslims often fall short when up against the other communities.(Hasan, 2018) Reality dictates that Muslims are disproportionately underrepresented in a composition for

professional and technical courses. In other words, fewer Muslims than their share of the population are enrolling in such courses. Therefore, fair competition producing fair outcomes prevents the Muslim population from increasing; instead, their percentage reaches such low levels that even one Muslim is unable to fill a seat due to the unproportionally unfair competition. This is one of the main logical explanations for Muslims' poor educational performance. (Saha, 2020) People in both urban and rural regions started to understand the value of education. The number of females enrolled in schools and higher education institutions has increased. Muslim women's lives have undergone gradual changes since, for a very long time, they were kept in the background and led submissive lives. Muslim women often get used to this way of life and find it difficult to accept change. Few Muslim women work in high-status positions, and their engagement in educational activities has been minimal. Generally, they are self-employed or are involved in home-based employment. The drop-out rate among them rises as a result of this. The parents share the opinion that daughters should not pursue education. Even when females enrol in schools, there is a significant dropout rate, with marriage being the main cause. Muslim girls are leaving schools at a higher rate because their parents feel that marriage should begin while a girl is still young (Shazli & Asma, 2015).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

The researcher has tried find out the various Educational Problems among the Muslim girls Students at secondary and higher secondary school in the district of Paschim Medinipur through the present study. Therefore the researcher selected the following as her research title: “**Educational problems of Muslim girl’s students at secondary and higher secondary school education of Paschim Medinipur district in west Bengal**”.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE:

Mollah (2018), in his paper “Status of Muslim women in west Bengal” has tried to trace out the actual status of Muslim women in West Bengal. The author also focused on education, socioeconomic, employment picture, health and political awareness status among the Muslim women in Bengal. He has concluded his paper with giving some suggestions.

Selvan (2017). Unplanned families, a lack of emphasis on educating females, parents who are unaware of the value of higher education, inadequate transportation options in rural regions, and other problems are some of the influencing elements that have a negative impact on girls seeking higher education there.

Bano (2017). In India, the literacy rates of Muslim men and women are lower than those of Hindus, Jains, Christians, Sikhs, and Buddhists, as well as Muslim women. In comparison to men and women from all other groups, women fall behind.

DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY: The term “delimitation” means to select certain boundaries for the study. This investigation was delimited to both urban and rural secondary level schools of Purulia district.

- **Sample:** -The researcher has selected only 200 students (Urban and Rural) of standard VIII from the secondary schools (Urban and Rural) and 70 teachers of those schools (Urban and Rural) of Purulia district.
- **Area:** -The researcher delimited the area and took only 5 schools of the mentioned district due to lack of time period. Three Rural schools and Two Rural School were taken.
- **Statistical Techniques:** -The researcher has used Mean, S.D. ‘t’-Test to analysis and represent the collected data in her present student.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

This article details a research looking at the difficulties Muslim females face in attending upper secondary schools in West Bengal's Paschim Medinipur District. It focuses on the difficulties faced by Muslim females seeking higher education in the area, both in the rural and urban areas. So, the study mainly intends to fulfil the following objectives:

- 1) To find out the differences between Minority Boys and Girls Students' regarding their Educational Problems at secondary and higher secondary school education in the district of Paschim Medinipur.
- 2) To find out the differences between Rural and Urban of Minority Community Students regarding their Educational Problems at secondary and higher secondary school education in the district of Paschim Medinipur.
- 3) To find out the differences between Urban Girls and Rural Girls Students of Muslim regarding their Educational Problems at secondary and higher secondary school education in the district of Paschim Medinipur.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY:

- H01: There is no significant difference between Minority Boys and Girls Students regarding their Educational Problems at secondary and higher secondary school education in the district of Paschim Medinipur
- H02: There is significant difference between Rural and Urban Minority Community Students regarding their Educational Problems at secondary and higher secondary school education in the district of Paschim Medinipur.
- H03: There is significant difference between Urban Girls and Rural Girls Students of Muslim regarding their Educational Problems at secondary and higher secondary school education in the district of Paschim Medinipur.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

Method of the Study: The present study is Descriptive type in nature. Descriptive type survey method has been used in this study. Therefore, naturally different tools, techniques, strategies and methods of Descriptive survey type research have been used to collect analysis and interpret the data. This study was conducted to identify Various Educational Problems of Muslim Girls Student at secondary and higher secondary school education in the district of Paschim Medinipur. To achieve this objective Quantitative research method was opted.

POPULATION AND SAMPLE OF THE STUDY:

The target learners' population in this study was all the students who were studying in Standard class ix-xii in present academic year i.e. 2020-2021. Although the researcher has drawn a sample of 200 Students of Secondary and higher secondary schools which are situated in the district of Paschim Medinipur (both Urban and Rural area) in West Bengal.

- **Tools Used:** The investigator employed self-constructed questionnaire for collecting of needed data. This self-constructed questionnaire has been made standardised by finding out the reliability and validity of it. Reliability of the questionnaire was assessed using the split-half approach.
- **Statistical Techniques:** Gathered data were analysed with SPSS 17 software package. Descriptive statistics and t test have used for the data analysis.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS:

Table 1: Shows the difference between Minority Boys and Girls Students regarding their Educational Problems at secondary and higher secondary school education in the district of Paschim Medinipur.

Gender	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error Mean	df	t-value
Boys	79	193.19	24.02	3.23	198	0.91
Girls	121	196.42	24.52	3.52		

From the above table it is observed that the calculated t-value (0.91) is lower than table value at 0.05 level of significance (1.96 at 0.05 level of significance). Therefore, the result is not significant and it indicates that there is no significant difference between Minority Boys and Girls Students regarding their Educational Problems. Hence, the Null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 2: Shows the difference between Rural and Urban Minority Community Students regarding their Educational Problems at secondary and higher secondary school education in the district of Paschim Medinipur

Area	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error Mean	df	t-value
Rural	119	196.81	25.36	4.10	198	1.17
Urban	81	192.70	22.62	3.50		

From the above table it is observed that the calculated t-value(1.17) is lower than table value at 0.05 level of significance(1.96 at 0.05 level of significance). Therefore, the result is not significant and it indicates that there is no significant difference between Minority Rural and Urban Students regarding their Educational Problems. Hence, the Null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 3: Shows the difference between Urban Girls and Rural Girls Students of Minority Community regarding their Educational Problems at secondary and higher secondary school education in the district of Paschim Medinipur.

Girls	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error Mean	df	t-value
Rural	56	189.38	21.79	13.12	119	3.033
Urban	65	202.49	25.26	4.32		

The statistically calculated t-value is .3.033 which is not significant at 0.05 levels with 119 df. Thus, null hypothesis which states that there is no significant between Minority Urban Girls and Rural Girls regarding their Educational Problems. Hence, the Null hypothesis is accepted.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

The following limitations have been found in the present Study: 1) Due to shortage of time the researcher has conducted his study only 200 Students of secondary schools in the district of Purulia. For this delimitation, the findings of the study have been found like above. 2) As the present study has been delimited to the area of Purulia district only, therefore such kind of findings have been found through the present study. 3) Due to shortage of time the researcher has conducted his study only 5 (Urban and Rural) Schools in the district of Purulia. For this delimitation, the findings of the study have been found like above. 4) The researcher has conducted his study at Elementary level in the district of Purulia. For this delimitation, the findings of the study have been found like above.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FURTHER STUDY:

- 1) A similar study can be conducted by including larger samples from various areas.
- 2) A similar study can be conducted on parents to find out the attitude of them towards the Educational Problems of Minority Community Students at Elementary Level.
- 3) A similar study can be conducted at Secondary or Higher Level in the district of Purulia
- 4) A similar study can be conducted at different District to find out the Educational Problems of Minority Community at Elementary level.
- 5) A similar study can be conducted at different States to find out the Educational Problems of Minority Community at Elementary level.

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